

EPIC TRADITIONS IN THE WORK OF SABIR SAYKALI IN UZBEK LITERATURE

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Abstract. *The traditions of Uzbek folklore and epics date back to BC. Epic writing developed through Uzbek folk books, and "traveling plots" were based on them. The geography of "Traveling Plots" was wide and was reflected in the literature of the peoples of the Middle and Near East. Similar epics in Hindi, Jewish, Urdu, Georgian, Armenian, Turkish, Kurdish, Azerbaijani, Tajik, Uzbek languages, "Yusuf and Zulayho", "Tahir and Zuhra", "Ashiq Gharib and Shahsanam", stories like "Bahrom and Gulandom", "Bahrom and Dilorom" and others were created.*

Among these epics, "Bahrom and Dilorom" (or Gulandom) has its own characteristics. The plot of Bahram was first reflected in written works on the history of Iranian kings such as "Khudaynamak", "Sirrul mulukul ajam", "Tarihi rusul va muluk". The story of Bahram Gor entered the fiction literature through the work "Shahnoma" by Abulqasim Firdavsi. Bahram's plot was given a big place in the composition of the Eastern Khamsha. The creation of Nizami Ganjavi's "Haft Paykar", Khusrav Dehlavi's "Hasht Bihisht", and Alisher Navoi's "Sab'ai Sayyar" epics aroused interest and admiration among creators. These epics laid the foundation stone for the traditions of Uzbek epics. The principles of the epic were developed.

Keywords: *epic, short stories, folk book, folklore materials, orientalist, heroic epic, romantic epics.*

The fiction literature of the XVII-XVIII centuries is famous for tazkiranavis, compilation of devon, creation of written versions of epics and short stories. During this period, dozens of war novels, romantic and heroic epics of historical content, "Sayyod va Hamro", "Asli va Karam", "Sanobar", "Yusufbek va Akhmedbek", "With Alibek" and "Sanobar", epics like "Bolibek", "Khurshid and Malikai Dilorom", their folklore and folk book variants were spread. Especially, starting from the 17th century, a number of Uzbek poets created examples of artistic works that had their own characteristics based on rich folklore materials, and in some cases, written literary sources.

These works are a special type of epic creation and occupy an important place in the history of our folklore and written literature. German Vamberi, an orientalist who studied the history and culture of Central Asia in the middle of the 19th century, wrote about folk novels that were widespread among the people: "Uzbeks have countless fiction novels, and in them "You can find many scenes that reflect the national feeling and pride, bravery and heroism of Uzbeks."

Folklorist M. Saidov studies Uzbek folk epics in 5 types: 1) heroic epics ("Alpomish", "Oysuluv"); 2) love epics ("Tahir and Zuhra"); 3) romantic epics ("Fairy of Gulnor", "Shirin and Sugar", "Ravshan"); 4) war stories ("Yusuf and Ahmed", "Alibek and Bolibek"); 5) historical epics ("Tulumbi", "Shaibani Khan"). Romantic epics are epics of the type of folk books, which were created under the influence of folk novels.

It is known that in the history of Uzbek literature, there are many anonymous works with unknown authors. A number of folk books are also such works. They do not indicate the time,

place, author, or even the scribe of this work. For example, the authors of works in the form of Uzbek folk books such as "Ashiq Gharib va Shahsanam", "Tahir va Zuhra", "Sanobar", "Malikai Dilnavoz", "Yusufbek va Ahmadbek" are still unknown. The author of "Yusufbek and Ahmadbek" is the 18th century poet Qurbanali Ma'rufiy, the author of "Sanobar" is Shaydaiy.

When the author of "Sayyod wa Hamro" is called Shohbanda, we use only the Turkmen versions of these works. Uzbek versions of works of the same name remain anonymous works. Once upon a time, these works became popular as examples of folklore, passed to the status of folk books in the performance of storytellers, narrators, and became folk books in the process of literary processing after being read. Therefore, it can be said that the creators of some of these works were short stories and narrations, and some of them have specific authors.

A number of folk books were created based on written sources. In the work, the heroism of the people is not exaggerated, the characters are depicted as given to very delicate, sentimental feelings, the poetic style typical of written literary works, the characteristics of the book language are clearly visible, the poetic fragments are presented in classical poetic genres and forms, and this shows that such works have a clear literary source.

We will clarify this idea through the analysis of the works of the poet Sabir Saykaliy Hisariy, who lived in the 18th century, namely the epic "Bahrom and Gulandom".

Sabir Saykali Hisori is one of the talented poets who left a mark in the history of Uzbek literature. His works include 1 epic - "Kissai Shahzoda Bahrom va Malikai Gulandom", "Kissai Hamra va Hurliq", "Ravzat ush-shuhado", "Akhtamnama", "Vaisul Qaran", "Zaynul Arab". It is also mentioned that Saykali was the author of the saga "Qissai Ibrahim Adham".

Saykali's epic "The Tale of Prince Bahram and Gulandom" is especially famous, it is widely read in manuscripts and printed copies. However, during the period of independence, Saykali's literary activities and works were widely studied and duly evaluated. Initially, his personality and some of his works were mentioned in the classes of literature teachers, and since the 50s, extensive research studies were conducted to study his oeuvre.

In Uzbek literature, in the years of independence Sabir Saykali's work was comparatively studied by Ph.D. M. Muhiddinov. The scientist made scientific conclusions about the development of the plot "Bahrom and Gulandom" in Uzbek literature, the analysis of all epics in this plot, the biography of the poets who created the epic.

According to Professor M. Muhiddinov, R. Aliev, who first tackled this topic in his candidate's dissertation on "Saikali and his epic "Bahrom and Gulandom" (Tashkent, 1964. Inv. R.D. 943) the content of the epics "The story of Bahrom and Gulandom" by Sabir Saykali is similar to the content of the Persian epics "Prince Bahram and Malikai Gulandom". However, it cannot be said that the origin of the plot of these works has not been discussed, as well as the different aspects of the plot of epics have been clearly revealed. It is known from the research that Saykali lived and created in Hisar at the end of the 18th century, he lived with material and spiritual difficulties, he suffered from the fact that his dreams did not come true in life, and he complained about his marriage in painful verses such as:

How many people did this era bring?

When I wanted to come,

he gave me an admonishment.

Again:

It's amazing faith, I'm so unlucky,

I'm sorry to be left behind.

Nevertheless, he highly valued the spiritual power of fiction, consciously used it to reflect the events of his time, socio-aesthetic views, and created several works.

As stated in the textbook "History of Uzbek Literature" in volume V, in a number of stories and short stories of Saykali, as a result of the limited worldview of the poet, the depiction of Sufi inclinations, submission to fate, piety, and patriotism takes the main place. However, the religious views advanced in "Kitobi Saykali" and other short poetic stories cannot determine the leading feature of the poet's work. In our eyes, Saykali appears mainly as a professional artist of his time with a progressive mindset and a wide field of observation.

In Uzbek literature, the study of Saykali's work is connected with his epic work "Bahrom and Gulandom".

Not only Uzbek, but also Russian and foreign literary critics have paid attention to Saykali's work.

In 1967, orientalist H.G. Korogli in his article "Saikali's epics "Bahram and Gulandom" and its source", showed that the source of Saykali's epic is a Persian prose story that is widely popular among the people and has been lithographed several times, and compared the plots of these two works and identified their similarities. At the same time, the author notes the characteristics of Saykali's style. However, H.G. Korogli is not interested in where the prose story is taken from.

In the article "On the Persian and Georgian versions of Bahrom and Gulandom", the Georgian literary scholar A.A. Gvakharia informs that there is a Persian poetic version of the story in addition to the prose version, the author of which is Muhammad Amin. According to him, copies of this saga are kept in the manuscript funds of Dushanbe and Tbilisi. Also, it is said that the story of Muhammad Amin was reported in Ryo and Ete catalogs. At the same time, A.A. Gwahariya talks about the sources of the plot, and also cites the opinion that it is a reworked version of the Iranian literary critic Mohammad Ja'far Mahjoub.

Professor M. Muhiddinov reports about Kadir Fattahi Qazi's research on this topic in the monograph "Nurli Qalblar Gulshan" (T., 2007, p. 111). According to the book, Qadir Fattahi Qazi, who conducted research on the Kurdish version of "Bahrom and Gulandom", translated and analyzed the Kurdish epic and compared it with the Persian one. Said Nasafi: "Several books have come down to us since the 10th century, the most important of which are "Iskandarnama" ("The Story of Rum"), "Khamsa Janganmasi", "Qirq Toti", "Chahor Dervish", "Bahram and Gulandom", "Hotami Toyi", "Epic of Alisher Arslan", and some of the aspects of "Bahram and Gulandom" are similar to the epic "Vis and Romin" (Fakhriddin Gurgoni - 11th century), but that it underwent changes in the following centuries. Scholars who have studied the works of Sabir Saykali directly pay attention to the "traveling plots" in the epics and the sources of the origin of the epics.

The following conclusions can be drawn from the opinions of Said Nasafi, Qadir Fattohi Qazi and Manuchehr Marzuvi: 1) The period of emergence of the "Bahram and Gulandom" plot goes back to the X-XI centuries. 2) This epic, like other examples of folklore, was born on the basis of folk fantasy. We agree with this opinion. The fact that the saga appeared before the 13th century is also confirmed by the information at the beginning of the Persian version, "Ammo roviyani akhbar va naqilani osor dar" "Jome'-ul karayat ovardaanki...". Because it was found that "Jome'-ul Narayat" (a collection of various legends and stories circulating among the people) was written in the 13th century. It should also be said that some of the epics that appeared as examples

of folklore were created under the influence of written literature. "Bahram and Gulandom" is one of such stories and it differs from "Chor Dervish" and "Amir Arslan" in this respect.

From the above points, it is clear that this epic is Persian in origin, and it is widespread among the peoples of the Near East (Uzbek, Georgian, Kurdish and Khakoza), but the plot is not the same everywhere. For example, the plot of the Kurdish version is very different compared to the Persian and Uzbek versions, new characters, new events are introduced, episodes are analyzed differently.

Professor M. Muhiddinov studied the materials related to Saykali's work and made the following conclusion based on the above points: Uzbek copies of "Bahrom and Gulandom" are also diverse. Until now, three epics were known in Uzbek language under the name "Bahrom and Gulandom" (the works of Saykali and Fazil Yoldosh oglu and the prose translation of Sidkiy Khandayliqi). But checks show that there is another Uzbek epic "Bahrom and Gulandom" under inventory number 719 in the manuscript fund of the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Abu Rayhan Beruni of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan.

The author (or narrator) of this saga is unknown. It is written with a mixture of prose and verse in its structure, and it is close to "Bahram and Gulandom" by Fazil Yoldosh's son. The work was probably written by a Bakhshi at the end of the 19th century, as the year of copying (1984-1986) indicates.

The Russian scientist, ethnographer N.P. Reacting Ostroumov's conclusions in this regard make the following points. N.P. Ostroumov's work entitled "Narodnye skazki sartov" (Etnograficheskie materialy. Vypusk II. Tashkent. 1893. p. 8.) is also about "Prince Bahrom" (Sarevich shahzade Bahrom), his story was passed from mouth to mouth among the people. The information about his journey is given and the plot of the epic is described. It is known from the plot that it is an oral interpretation of "Prince Bahram and Malikai Gulandom".

As a result of studying the works of the authors of the epics "Bahrom and Gulandom", it was found that the development of the events of the works "Bahrom and Gulandom" in Uzbek literature, as well as having many commonalities in terms of the plot line, there are many different aspects and peculiarities. These different aspects did not fail to influence the ideological content of the epics and the essence of symbols. In all epics, the details that create the beginning of the exposition and the knot of events are the same. Although Bahram's adventures, episodes representing his heroism, conclusion and solution, the participation of the characters in the development of the main event are similar in these works, but the details of the development of the plot, the justification of the events, the actions and speeches of the characters, the formation and concretization of the characters, the symbols differ in the use of literary methods to reveal their inner world, in the style of images. Therefore, each of them has a special aesthetic value and influence. When studying the work of Saykali, one should not forget that the scientific works devoted to the analysis of the works written on the basis of the plot of Bahrom Gor. Include the works of Academicians I. Orbeli, V. Zohidov, professors G. Karimov, H. Yakubov, A. Dehoti, A. Mulkamanov, R. Aliev.

There are no principled differences that contradict each other in the works devoted to the issue of the plot of Bahrom Gor and its spread and development in Eastern literature. Most of them support each other in the main essence of the issue and its interpretation and clarify the issue from different angles. Even so, there are opinions that contradict the truth in some places. Some studies have allowed one-sidedness in working on the topic, or have hurried to make superficial

conclusions without a deep approach to the facts. A. Dehoti, in his article dedicated to "Haft Paykar", tries to justify Nizami's originality, puts him above Firdavsi and unreasonably belittles the content of "Shahnama". Although this tradition is not so many, it can be felt in the works of several other famous orientologists.

According to the opinion of Professor M. Muhiddinov, the development of the plot of the story of Bahrom Gor was not investigated in all its aspects.

In Uzbek literature, in addition to the plot "Bahrom and Kanizak" ("Bahrom and Azoda" in Firdavsi, "Bahrom and Fitna" in Nizami, "Bahrom and Dilorom" in Khusrav Dehlavi and Navoi) The plot of "Bahrom and Gulandom" is also widespread. The plot of "Bahrom and Kanizak" was worked on in "Khamsa" and took a wide place in classical literature and thus spread among the people, while "Bahrom and Gulandom" first gained fame in folk art and then moved to written literature and from there passed back to folklore. In Uzbek literature, there are mostly folk versions of works written on the plot of "Bahrom and Gulandom". Although this plot appeared earlier in the folklore of the eastern peoples, it first entered our literature as an example of written literature in the 18th century through Sabir Saykali's epic "Bahrom and Gulandom". Interest in studying the works of Sabir Saykali is also related to the study of the plot of Bahrom Gor in Uzbek literature. Although the plot of Bahrom Gor is considered a plot in the language of a folk book, it reflects the influence and signs of classic literature. We can clearly see this especially in Sabir Saykali's saga. This, of course, represents the connection and relationship between written literature and oral creativity.

The study of Saykali's biography and a series of epics is still left out of the attention of literary scholars. Also, the saga "Bahrom and Gulandom" has not been analyzed in detail in all aspects. Even so, we do not have the opportunity to study this work extensively and deeply. Regarding the plot of Saykali's epic, its connection and differences with the plot of other works of the same name, if the poet's skill in this regard is included in the analysis, it will be possible to study the unique features of his work.

Studying the skill of Saykali's epic writing is also important for the research of the next epics.

In conclusion, it should be said that the study of Saykali's work has been revived since the 1950s. He lived in Hisar at the end of the 18th century and wrote about the problems of social life in his realistic verses:

How many people did this era bring?

Whom I wanted, he gave me admonishment

In a number of stories and short stories of Saykali, the Sufi views and moods of Qalandarism occupy the main place in the poet's worldview. The leading features of the poet's work are reflected in the ideas put forward in "Kitobi Saykali" and other short poetic stories.

In our opinion, Saykali appears mainly as a professional artist of his time with a progressive mindset and a wide field of observation. This can be confirmed during the analysis of his great work - "Bahrom and Gulandom".

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